

Recommended citation: Glessmer, M. S., & Seifert, C. (2017). E-Assessments to Increase the Perceived Importance of Mathematics in the Introductory Phase of Engineering Education via Bridging Tasks . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1549-1556). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698623.

E-Assessments to increase the perceived importance of Mathematics in the introductory phase of Engineering Education via bridging tasks

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a project designed to increase motivation and perceived impact of mathematics for engineering students in the first year of engineering studies at Hamburg University of Technology.

The aim of this project is to demonstrate to students the importance of mathematics for any engineering subject, specifically for mechanical and electrical engineering as the main subjects of their respective study programs. This is achieved by posing problems linking both mechanical and electrical engineering, respectively, to mathematics via e-assessment. By explicitly showing the relevance of mathematics for their chosen major subject, we increase student motivation during mathematics classes and, therefore, their performance.

We comment on why we chose e-assessment as the tool to implement the applied problems, bridging the gap between mathematics and the fundamental subject of the two study programs, provide examples of the kind of problems we have found to be successful in achieving our goals and discuss our experiences.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Gender and Diversity, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: engineering education, e-assessment, introductory phase

INTRODUCTION

At many universities, and especially in the introductory phase, courses are taught simultaneously for students of different major subjects of study due to organisational reasons. A typical example is a mathematics class for first year engineering students which, for example at Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), is attended by students from 12 different study programs, ranging from civil engineering to mechanical engineering, process engineering and mechatronics to computer

science, environmental engineering and logistics. Thus, these courses are attended by hundreds of participants (1300 in our case) which are very inhomogeneous with regards to skills, knowledge, interests, and motivation for learning mathematics [4].

In order to deal with such a heterogeneous audience, the obvious solution for the lecturer would be a reduction of the material and possible applications to the largest common denominator, which typically is just the pure material. As a consequence, the students typically do not feel that the course is of practical importance for their personal studies, which results in decreased engagement in the course and frustration on all sides.

In this article, we present a project where we, within the same class, pose different problems to students of different study courses. These problems come from applications specific to the study programs but are, when reduced to their mathematical core and needed skills, equivalent in formulation and method of solving for all study programs. In order to enable students to use a mastery approach towards learning mathematics, they need to be able to recognize how content relates to their own goals [16]; that being able to “do” mathematics is worth the effort given the value they attribute to their chosen subject [12]. Therefore, we point out the necessity of learning mathematics in order to excel at their own topics, supporting the development of their professional identity [11]. Also in order for content from one course to be accessible in a different one, connections between courses have to be made explicit [15]. Lastly it is important that students attribute successes to their own efforts [17] and hence experience competence [13]. Supporting students during their first year of study is important because they often feel isolated and under extreme pressure [4, 2], need support to study continuously [3] and wish for feedback [19].

Due to the size of the course, the problems are posed within an e-assessment platform and available information on the students' major subject is used to assign the appropriate tasks. The idea to use e-assessment as a tool to assess students and train students individually is certainly not new [18, 9, 7]. However, our approach is new in the sense that we use specific tasks for specific study programs within one and the same class.

In Section 1 we describe the framework of the course as well as its organisational details, and also present the key facts to the innovation. Section 2 motivates the choice of e-assessment as the tool for implementation instead of including the problems into the lectures or other alternatives. Concrete examples of tasks are given in Section 3, followed by comments on evaluation and our experiences. In the final Section 5 we discuss our project, the obtained results and give a short outlook.

1 THE COURSE AND THE INNOVATION

1.1 Boundary conditions of the innovation

We focus on the mathematics course for first-year engineering students at TUHH. It is a mandatory course for around 1300 students from 12 different study programs. Although it is a mandatory course, it is not a major subject of any of the study programs. Hence, in order to awake and subsequently increase the students' motivation, we have to relate the course material to the students' study programs, assuming they chose those based on interest for the subject.

The course is taught within 2 large lectures per week, one large exercise session, 40 tutorial sessions with approximately 30 students each, weekly problems sheets (where solutions are provided later on) and weekly individual randomized problems on an e-assessment platform for somewhat continuous assessment and formative feedback during the course.

We are using e-assessment as a formative tool in class since 2010 [8]. Concerning the bridging tasks with applied problems linking the content of different courses, we are still in the implementation phase, and we are incrementally building more tasks for different target groups. During winter semester 2016/17, we posed six problems coming from mechanics applications and six problems coming from electronics applications in parallel. During the previous academic year, we only had applied problems related to mechanics, where we had five problems in total.

1.2 Key facts of the innovation

In a first step, we divided the course participants – i.e., the 12 study programs – into two different groups: those students having mechanics as one of their major subjects (e.g. mechanical engineering, ship building, ...), and those students having electronics as one of their major subjects (e.g. electrical engineering, ...). In this step, we implemented applied problems related to mechanics as well as electronics.

In order to find appropriate and interesting applications for each of the groups, we first mapped the topics and the course schedules for the mathematics course with the schedules for mechanics and electronics. This was done by comparing course materials and creating a weekly schedule for all the three courses and identifying the mathematical content and concepts within the mechanics and electronics course for each week. After that we compared with the corresponding weekly mathematics schedule. Now, we tried to make the program of these three courses as coherent as possible by interchanging topics within courses. Note that this step required at least three lectures from different departments to communicate about the curriculum of the students. Additionally, the internal logical structure of each of the subjects had to be taken into account.

After having generated a schedule for the three courses, one can start developing problems suitable for the two groups. We emphasize that we are still dealing with one single mathematics course. Therefore, first we generated a mathematics problem suitable for the mathematical content. Then we rephrased this problem in a way that there is some relationship to the applied courses. For example, when the mathematical task is to solve a linear system of equations, the mechanics application could be the computation of the forces in a truss structure, whereas the electronics application could be the computation of currents in an electric circuit.

It may happen that for a given mathematical task there is no suitable application in one of the engineering fields, or even in neither. Then just the group for which an adequate task exists is asked to solve an applied problem, the other group (or groups) will still have to solve the “purely mathematical task” which would have been the default before our innovation.

In order to increase students' participation in solving these problems, apart from relating the mathematical content to their major subjects, we introduce incentives such as bonus points for the final exam for solving these problems (i.e., an optional incentive, [1]). Another possibility would be to include these problems into a formative part of the final evaluation (i.e., a mandatory incentive). This, however, depends on the rules and regulations for exams, and in our particular case we can only use optional incentives.

2 WHY CHOOSE E-ASSESSMENT

The first big design choice to make—while attempting to individualise students' mathematics teaching—was how to distribute the problems to the students, how to mark assignments and how to provide feedback. Below we will describe the reasons that led to us choosing e-assessment.

2.1 Advantages of e-assessment

Posing problems electronically has many advantages. First, every student can be identified uniquely by their user login. This gives the opportunity to automatically specify problems individually for every student, or groups of students, dependent on multiple possible criteria like their chosen major, their demonstrated level of skill, and many more.

There are quite a few assessment tools available on the market. In our case of mathematics instruction, many of the tools are based on computer algebra systems (CAS). Since CAS allow for random input parameters within problems, one obtains a large variety of realisations of the same problem very easily, so students cannot copy and paste solutions from their classmates and they have a large pool of similar tasks to practice with. The CAS can also automatically mark the students' answers. Furthermore, one can implement an automatic feedback based on the students' performance and the random input parameters. After finishing an assignment, the instructor can get an automatic item statistic for each task without further effort. Although all of these properties can be achieved also by pen-and-paper problems, the cost for creating an adequately large pool of problems, marking them and giving feedback does not scale with the size of the course, but rather stays constant. This makes this approach very attractive for large groups. Note that there are pools of problems available online. However, these problems still have to be adjusted to the concrete course taught due to possible differences in contents, notation, technical platforms used and many more reasons.

Due to the randomisation and individualisation, problems can be re-used: a student can have multiple attempts at the same assignment, working on different realisations of the problems in each attempt, without remembering the answer from previous attempts. So, the use of e-assessment with random inputs is very sustainable.

2.2 Disadvantages of e-assessment

Of course, there are also disadvantages when using e-assessment platforms. Especially when creating problems with random input parameters, there is a lot of effort to be done to obtain "nice" quantities (e.g. when generating a matrix with random elements but one is interested in the eigenvalues of the matrix, then the random elements of the matrix should be chosen in a way such that the eigenvalues are nice, i.e. integer-valued). Therefore, the initial effort for creating one realisation of a task to be used in e-assessment is indeed much higher than for pen-and-paper problems. However, it is important to keep in mind that a good task template with adequately chosen variable ranges generates many task realisations simultaneously.

Moreover, making use of an electronic platform always requires some sort of technical support for the platform. Even though this may be included in some commercial products, it has to be organised by the instructor in open source solutions and can in any case become a huge hassle if the system is not working as promised and hundreds of students call to inquire what is wrong and whether this will impact their grades.

For the students as users of the platform, the technical equipment to actually use the platform is required. Fortunately, many of the available systems are web-based, so one just needs a computer with access to the internet and an up-to-date browser, to which student have access [14, 20].

In summary, the disadvantages of e-assessment boil down to higher costs when creating the problems. Nevertheless, these higher costs pay off in the long run due to re-usability and the usability in large classes.

2.3 Why not include the applied problems into the lecture, exercise sessions or tutorials?

One may ask why we are not including the applied problems, bridging between mathematics and the engineering subject, within the lectures, exercises or tutorial sessions. The first reason is that due to students from 12 different study courses attending the lecture, not all students attend the same engineering classes (i.e. mechanics or electronics). Thus, when including a mechanics problem into the lecture, the students not attending mechanics will not necessarily be especially motivated to see mathematics they are not interested in in the first place applied to an engineering topic they are not interested in, either. And even if they are motivated to follow, they might, due to their missing background in mechanics, not be able to understand the problem appropriately. Moreover, to be fair, one would need to include applied problems for all groups, which would increase the volume of content to be dealt with during a lecture.

One could be tempted to include discussion of applied problems into the tutorial sessions instead of lectures, where the groups are much smaller. However, this would require tutorial sessions dedicated to specific study programs, which increases the organisational effort and may not be doable in practice (which is exactly the case at TUHH). Thus, from an organisational point of view, individualisation within the lectures, exercise class or tutorial session may be impossible.

3 EXAMPLES OF TASKS

In this section, we demonstrate two examples of problems for applied tasks.

3.1 Example: Periodic functions

One easy problem we posed was related to periodic functions with the intended learning outcome of familiarizing students with the interpretation of graphic displays of such functions. Students were asked to read the amplitude and the frequency off a given plot of a periodic function. The parameters of the function displayed in that plot varied to show either sine or cosine, an integer amplitude between -6 and 6 (excluding -1,0, and 1) and an integer period between 2 and 8. Furthermore, the range for the plot varied from half a period to 2 periods on different positions on the real axis.

To motivate this kind of task to students interested in mechanics, the students were told the given plot described the vertical position of a mass hanging on a spring pendulum as a function of time, and their task was to read off the parameters: How large is the oscillation of the mass around its position of rest? What's the period of the oscillation?

On the other hand, we put this problem into an electronics framework by considering an LC-circuit. The given plot was then describing the time-oscillating voltage and the students were asked to identify the amplitude and the frequency of the voltage.

Fig. 2. Pictures describing the applications for the problems. Left: spring pendulum. Middle: One possible graph. Right: LC-circuit.

3.2 Example: Solving linear systems

In this problem, the students were asked to solve a linear system of 6 equations in 6 unknowns, where the random entries of the coefficient matrix were “nice”.

The students from the group related to mechanics were asked to compute the forces at the trusses 1, 2, and 3 and the forces at the junction A (see Fig. 3). The size of the cuboid (i.e., a , b , and c) and the gravitational force were randomized.

The formulation for the group of students from electronics was the following: Given an electrical network with randomized voltage sources and resistances, compute the corresponding currents.

Fig. 3. The pictures describing the application for the problems on solving linear systems. Left: Sketch of a cuboid. Right: An electric network.

4 EVALUATION OF THE PROJECT

We restrict the evaluation of the project to the winter semester 2016/17. There, we had 1264 students registered for the e-assessment of the corresponding course at the platform. We asked three questions for evaluating the project. With a response rate of approximately 16%, students overwhelmingly agreed or were neutral to whether the applied tasks were helpful (89%), whether they helped transfer knowledge between courses (91%) and wanting more applied tasks (90%).

One may also ask the question of whether students were actually willing to use the e-assessment platform. In the course under consideration the students were asked to solve weekly assignments, 12 in total, where they could earn 3 points per assignment (so 36 points in total). Figure 4 shows a histogram of the points earned, so students actually worked continuously on the platform. Around 2/3 of the students got at least half of the points. This corresponds to a typical drop-out rate of 1/3 of the students in this course who chose to leave the study program at TUHH.

Fig. 4. Histogram of students earning e-assessment points.

5 DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, several tasks needed to be done in order to realise such a project. All of these tasks required personal and technical resources. In our case, we had two employees working part-time (50%) on that project for one year. Moreover, we had student tutors for implementing the problems at the e-assessment platform. Furthermore, the e-assessment platform itself causes costs (either in support for open source systems, or in licence costs for commercial systems). However, these costs have to be compared with the number of students (around 1300) and the possibility to give continuous individual feedback on their performance at this course. This would not have been possible with pen-and-paper solutions. The personal impression (as a lecturer for this course, and the parallel engineering courses) was that the bridging tasks helped students to motivate for the mathematics class, and also to transfer knowledge from one class to the other. So, in our opinion, the costs are worth it. Possible adverse effects of incrementally accommodating students more and more every year are discussed elsewhere [5, 6], however we take care to not fall into the traps described there. To conclude, we are very satisfied with the outcome of this project and will continue to work in this direction. Moreover, we are willing to cooperate with lecturers from other universities on such a kind of project.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from Stifterverband für die Deutsche Wissenschaft through their teaching innovation fellowship program.

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